

Krichewsky-Wegener, L. & Brück, L. (2023). Using smartphones for learning: A case study on the impact of digitalization on apprenticeship in the informal sector in Ghana. In V. Tütlys, L. Vaitkutė & C. Nägele (Eds.), *Vocational Education and Training Transformations for Digital, Sustainable and Socially Fair Future. Proceedings of the 5th Crossing Boundaries Conference in Vocational Education and Training, Kaunas, 25. – 26. May* (pp. 237–244). European Research Network on Vocational Education and Training, VETNET, Vytautas Magnus University Education Academy, Institute of Educational Science. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7821856>

Using Smartphones for Learning: A Case Study on the Impact of Digitalization on Apprenticeship in the Informal Sector in Ghana

Krichewsky-Wegener, Léna

krichewsky@iit-berlin.de, Institute for Innovation and Technology (iit) Berlin

Brück, Lukas

Lukas.brueck@gfa-group.de, GFA Consulting Group

Abstract

Increased use of smartphones in everyday life in Sub-Saharan Africa is commonly presented as an opportunity for learners in the informal sector to gain access to new knowledge and skills. At the same time, it is associated with the risk of creating new dynamics of marginalization (digital divide). Based on a case study conducted in Ghana, the aim of this paper is to gain a better understanding of how digital technologies affect patterns of inequalities in the particular context of apprenticeships in the informal sector. The analysis of interviews conducted with Mastercraft Persons and apprentices follows the expansive learning theory in the tradition of the cultural-historical activity theory developed by Engeström. As result, three patterns of change of the learning and training culture in workshops of the informal sector are identified, which have different effects on the digital divide between apprentices who have a smartphone and those who don't.

Keywords

informal apprenticeship, digitalization, expansive learning theory

1 Context

In the context of development policy, digitalization is commonly presented as a major opportunity to increase the access to and the quality of education and training, especially for vulnerable groups in society (e.g. EC, 2017). Critical voices, however, point to the risks associated with it in terms of “a further widening of the digital divide (along North-South, rural/urban, affluent/poor, powerful/marginalised and gender lines)” and “increasing educational and social inequities” (Langthaler & Bazafkan, 2020, p.16). The aim of this paper is to gain a better understanding of how digital technologies affect patterns of inequalities in the particular context of apprenticeships in the informal sector. It is based on a case study conducted in Ghana in August 2022.

In Ghana, as in many other countries in Sub-Saharan Africa, apprenticeships in the informal sector are the main avenue for young people to develop vocational skills, especially for those with no formal education or lacking sufficient capital to participate in formal vocational education and training (VET). Apprenticeships in the informal sector are not

regulated by the state and are based exclusively on work-based learning. Learning and training practices are embedded in a social and cultural context characterized by a strong hierarchy between Mastercraft Persons (MCP), chief, senior and junior apprentices. Learning is problem-based and can be described well with the model of legitimate peripheral participation into a community of practice (Lave & Wenger, 1991). Asking questions to more experienced apprentices and to the MCPs is usually the apprentices' main strategy for building new knowledge, as books or other media are rarely used in apprenticeships (Allah-Mensah & McGrath, 2021; Jaarsma et al., 2011). Smartphones, as the main devices used by the population in Sub-Saharan Africa to access the internet, can be a transformative factor by providing both MCPs and learners alike access to new sources of information and new forms of communication.

While mobile phones are widespread in Ghana, with 130 mobile phone subscription per 100 inhabitants, the share of internet users reached 58% of the population in 2020 and according to our data, not every apprentice or MCP has access to a smartphone or let alone laptop (ITU, 2022). Inequalities related to the use of smartphones can be traced back in particular to the costs of mobile data and the lack of literacy and basic digital skills, but also in some cases to parents not wanting their adolescent children to be exposed to other viewpoints or religious beliefs. This paper addressed the following research question: How are smartphones used as learning devices in the context of apprenticeships in the informal sector and to what extent can we observe effects on patterns of social exclusion?

2 Approach

2.1 Theoretical framework

The theoretical framework used to describe and understand the disruptive potential of digital technologies for learning in the informal sector is based on the expansive learning theory in the tradition of the cultural-historical activity theory (Engeström & Sannino, 2010). Key premises of this theory resonate well with core characteristics of the study object:

- the focus on *communities* as learning subjects: learning in the informal sector strongly relies on social interactions between MCPs and apprentices, who for a community of practice;
- learning is about *transforming and creating culture*: the use of smartphones for learning purposes can be considered as a change affecting the learning and training practices and thus the learning/training culture specific to apprenticeships in the informal sector;
- learning is understood in a broad sense, not only as an intentional and unilateral transmission of skills and knowledge, but also as a more or less implicit process of practice-related knowledge creation: “the learners construct a new object and concept for their collective activity, and implement this new object and concept in practice” (Engeström & Sannino, 2010, p.2). As in the case of smartphones being introduced at the workplace, there is no right or wrong way to use them, but rather a challenge of inventing new usages and associated skills: “Nobody knows exactly what needs to be learned. The design of the new activity and the acquisition of the knowledge and skills it requires are increasingly intertwined. In expansive learning activity, they merge” (Engeström & Sannino, 2010, p.3).

We intend to use the model of activity systems as heuristic framework to describe how smartphones emerge as a new “instrument” for learning and training in the context of apprenticeships in the informal sector.

Figure 1

General model of an activity system (Engestrom, 1987, p. 78)

Fig. 1. General model of an activity system (Engeström, 1987, p. 78).

Based on this theoretical framework, the research question can be reformulated: How are learners who do not own a smartphone included in the expansive learning process and what are the implications of the newly emerging learning cultures for them in terms of participation and access to skills?

2.2 Methodological approach

The case study is based on the re-analysis of data collected in Ghana in the framework of a research assignment for the German development cooperation in August 2022.¹ The assignment aimed at exploring the use of digital devices in apprenticeship in the informal sector in order to identify the potential for skills development interventions in Sub-Saharan Africa. Ghana was chosen as a case study because apprenticeship is well developed in the informal sector and the use of smartphones is widespread. Data was collected from MCPs and apprentices in three different trades: dressmakers, beauticians and hairdressers, and electricians. Data collection included four focus groups with MCPs as well as group interviews conducted with apprentices in 14 different workshops in Accra and the Northern city of Tamale. A total of 19 MCPs (47% women) and 61 apprentices (67% women) were interviewed. All the MCPs owned at least a smartphone, a few of them also a laptop or a tablet. Among the apprentices, 70% owned a smartphone and 11% a feature phone, with the latter allowing them to access pre-installed mobile applications such as WhatsApp. The remaining apprentices did not own a device that would enable them to access the internet.

The focus group and interview guidelines were focusing on the use of digital devices for working and for learning/training purposes, also addressing the challenges and opportunities associated with these use cases. The interviews and focus groups took place mainly in English, a local expert translating in some cases in Twi when interviewees did not feel fluent enough to answer questions in English.

The first step of the analysis followed the methodology of qualitative content analysis developed by Kuckartz (2014) in order to structure the material. In a second step, the activity system model was used to re-organise the data and identify patterns of social integration of apprentices not owning any digital device.

¹¹ The research question addressed in this paper was not part of the ToRs for this assignment. The results presented here engage the sole responsibility of the authors. They have not been published elsewhere.

3 Results

The expansive learning theory goes beyond Lave & Wenger (1991), not limiting social learning processes to the unidirectional movement from incompetency to competency implied in the legitimate-peripheral-participation model. Instead, it is much more likely that apprentices and MCPs alike, by their respective use of smartphones and conceptions about this device, shape the learning/training practices. Therefore, two interacting activity systems were defined, the apprentices' and the MCP's system, in order to describe how they are challenged by the emerging use of smartphones as learning devices (see table 1).

Table 1

Activity systems describing learning and training in apprenticeships in the informal sector in Ghana

“Nod”	Apprentices	MCP
Subject	Apprentices (seniors, juniors)	MCP
Object	Learning	Training/Teaching
Rules	Hierarchic relationships between MCP and senior/junior apprentices: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - learner asks questions to senior/MCP and learns through participant observation, imitation - learner depends on MCP to get a certificate and to get prepared for taking national examinations - learner pays training fees to the MCP. 	Hierarchic relationships between MCP and apprentices: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MCP assigns tasks to apprentices and teaches new skills problem-based; Qualification standards, as far as apprentices are prepared for national examinations; Need to safeguard a “good reputation” in order to continue attracting apprentices, who represent a cheap working force.
Community	Peers, possibly adults outside the workshop practicing the trade in their family	Other MCPs, trade association
Instruments	Paper and pencil, sometimes books, working tools	Paper, sometimes board, working tools
Division of labour	Apprentices work in production depending on their skills level, seniors train juniors	MCPs work in production, supervise seniors and teach selected skills themselves (e.g. the “basics” and /or most advanced skills)

Smartphones are new instruments introduced in the two activity systems by individuals (MCP and/or apprentices), complementing and to some extent replacing the “traditional” instruments (e.g. paper and pencil, books, working tools).

Smartphones have a potentially “disruptive” character clearly identified in the interviews by both MCPs and apprentices insofar as they are:

- challenging the traditionally hierarchic learning culture, where juniors learn from seniors and MCP, by opening up a new avenue to skills development (e.g. video tutorials): this is expressed in the debates among learners whether it is possible to learn without a MCP, or the fear expressed by MCP to have their authority questioned by learners and to fail to attract enough apprentices because apprentices could think that they can learn the trade online by themselves;
- interfere with the learning/training process if they are used as entertainment devices or without sufficient experience or digital literacy to distinguish between good and bad quality content: some MCPs complain about that, while apprentices admit that they look at series, chat with friends etc. during working hours or miss on sleep to use

- “midnight bundles”, cheap data bundles offered between midnight and 5 am to allow them affordable downloading of videos;
- creating conflicts and frustrations among apprentices between those who own a smartphone and those who don't;
 - opening up the communities to include more external members, thus increasing the competition among MCPs to attract “good” apprentices, putting pressure on them to take care of their image or reputation as trainers.
 - questioning the role of MCPs in determining the content of learning tasks and progression path.

Based on the qualitative content analysis of the interview data, we identify three typical ways of dealing with these disruptions by integrating or banning the use of smartphones into the learning/training activities. Each of these typical patterns has implications for reduction or widening social inequalities by contributing (or not) to the skills development of disadvantaged learners.

A first pattern, which was the most common in the workshops visited, integrates smartphones into learning and training practices by ensuring access for disadvantaged learners and inventing new forms of collective learning. As a result, the digital divide between those who own a smartphone and those who do not is reduced to some extent.

An example of integrating smartphones into teaching practices is provided by an electrician in Accra. He uses videos occasionally, for instance to demonstrate what he cannot show in practice:

“Respondent: For instance I tell the apprentices to look at a video on how to use a fire extinguisher when it comes to teaching health and safety.

Interviewer: On what smartphone do they watch the video?

Respondent: Usually they look at the video each on his own smartphone. If someone has no smartphone, he will look on the one of another apprentice. Or I will show it on my own or we look on a screen if there is one in the shop [i.e. one which was brought for repair]”
(Electrician MCP, Accra)

In all three trades, there are examples when learning with smartphones becomes a collective activity, with the MCP taking part alongside the apprentices:

“Sometimes Madam shows a new style on her smartphone. We discuss with her how it is made – because often you don't see the back, or the details. Last week we learned to make a corset, with the help of videos.” (Dressmaker apprentice, Accra)

This type of collective learning can be linked to changes in customer demand and working practices brought about by digitalization. When clients request for the replication of models found on Instagram or Pinterest, or when they bring in new types of electrical devices to be repaired, MCPs turn to the Internet to keep up with new techniques and solve unfamiliar problems. Social media and YouTube are the main sources of inspiration and know-how. Gathered around a smartphone or a tablet to watch a video or examine a picture, MCPs and apprentices form a community of practice that can be considered to extend beyond the workshop to integrate those who share their experience on the internet.

While the potentially distracting character of smartphones is acknowledged, some MCPs set rules to restrict the use of them for learning purpose only:

“It is a work place rule to put phones away and only revert to them when we need to refer to some material or make an urgent call. For instance, when Madam brings a picture or video to discuss it together.” (Dressmaker apprentice, Accra)

In some cases, MCPs give access to their own digital devices, provide a hotspot or share videos via Bluetooth to facilitate access of all their apprentices to digital learning content. In other cases, or in addition to this, apprentices also share their smartphones. In a hairdresser shop in Tamale, apprentices who own only a so-called “yam phone” (i.e. simple mobile phone without

Internet access) are allowed to use the smartphone of their colleagues when sharing free mobile data bundles with them:

“Interviewer: How do you use your phones for work?”

Respondent 1: We browse the internet for new styles and practice what we see on each other.

Respondent 2: We those with yam phones usually get free data from service providers, so we sometimes put our SIM cards in the smartphones of our colleagues so we can do our research.” (Hairdresser apprentice, Tamale)

Through these practices, apprentices who do not have a smartphone are not completely deprived of the benefits of accessing Internet for learning. They can learn basic digital skills, and some interviewees reported how senior apprentices had taught them to use YouTube to find “do-it-yourself”-videos to learn.

A second pattern, which remains almost a theoretical construct in the Ghanaian case study, would be the ban of smartphones from the workshop in order to avoid the changes that digitalization might bring. This could be the result of an MCP seeing smartphones as a distraction, a mere entertainment device. While there were no examples of MCPs completely ignoring or rejecting digitalization, there were some critical voices among the MCPs, who emphasised the importance of practical skills and did not see themselves as responsible for teaching digital skills to their apprentices:

“We have to train the trade skills, we are not here to train them to watch YouTube”
(Beautician, Accra)

As a consequence, learners do not experience any support to develop good learning strategies using the smartphone. If they do not own a device, they might lack any opportunity to use the Internet as a learning resource.

A third, pattern, situated between those two extremes, is characterized by a “laissez-faire” approach, tolerating individual use of smartphones at the workshop, but without integrating it into collective learning practices. For example, in one dressmaker workshop in Accra, of seven apprentices and one former apprentice, who had come to participate in the interview, only one did not own a smartphone. While the MCP owned a laptop, he didn’t use it actively for teaching, nor did the senior apprentice, who said:

“When I don’t know how to help, I tell the person to ask the Master” (dressmaking senior apprentice, Accra)

While the youngest apprentice, who did not own a smartphone, said that *“nobody taught [her] something using the phone”*, some apprentices reported looking for videos and pictures in order to learn about new trends and techniques by themselves.

For all the apprentices interviewed, the cost of mobile data was mentioned as the main barrier to using smartphones as learning devices. In the workshop mentioned above, the MCP used to provide access to mobile data, but this was not (only) used for learning purposes, as reported by his apprentices:

“The MCP sometimes buys data and you can use Wi-Fi if you contribute – but we used it too much to watch videos, so it isn’t that regular anymore.” (dressmaking apprentice, Accra)

As neither the MCP nor the senior apprentices actively use smartphone for teaching, apprentices not owning a smartphone do not access the Internet for learning. Using digital devices for learning is left to the responsibility of individual learners, who may lack the skills or motivation to do so. As a result, the digital divide risks widening.

4 Conclusion

A comparison of the three patterns of use of digital devices for learning and teaching in apprenticeship in the informal sector identified in this case study highlights the importance of embedding the use of digital technologies in social practices, taking into account the key role of MCPs in making the smartphone an *inclusive* learning device. When used as a tool for collective learning, smartphones provide apprentices with access to learning resources and an extended community of practice that goes beyond the boundaries of their workshop. Many examples were found, where apprentices who did not own a smartphone were included in the learning process, limiting the risk of a digital divide and subsequent social exclusion. However, in cases where MCPs have a negative attitude towards digital technologies, or simply ignore their learning potential, there is a high risk that learners deprived of internet access will be marginalized. As for those who can use their smartphone to access the internet, they may not be able to take full advantage of the learning potential of digital technologies due to a lack of digital learning skills and support to apply what they find on the Internet in practice.

The research methods used for this paper have a series of limitations. Among these, the most important is probably the loss of information induced, in some interviews, by the need to translate questions and answers. Moreover, a bias could exist because of the recruitment of interviewees. The MCPs were contacted via trade associations. As they were all active members of this trade association, they seemed particularly aware of skills development issues. This might explain that, overall, they had a positive attitude towards digitalization and were interested in using smartphones for teaching and learning. Different strategies could be used to further diversify the sample of interviewees for further studies. Another limitation of the study is that no data was collected to assess precisely the digital skills of MCPs and apprentices. A digital skills gap was therefore assessed only on the basis of the interviews. Further research is needed to better grasp all the consequences of digitalization in the informal sector in Ghana and other Sub-Saharan African countries.

References

- Alla-Mensah, J., & McGrath, S. (2021). A capability approach to understanding the role of informal apprenticeship in the human development of informal apprentices. *Journal of Vocational Education & Training*, 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13636820.2021.1951332>
- Engeström, Y. (1987). *Learning by expanding: An activity-theoretical approach to developmental research*. Orienta-Konsultit Oy.
- Engeström, Y., & Sannino, A. (2010). Studies of expansive learning: Foundations, findings and future challenges. *Educational Research Review*, 5(1), 1–24.
- European Commission (EC) (2017). *Digital4Development: Mainstreaming Digital Technologies and Services into EU Development Policy*. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/de/node/4100>
- Jaarsma, T., Maat, H., Richards, P., & Wals, A. (2011). The role of materiality in apprenticeships: The case of the Suame Magazine, Kumasi, Ghana. *Journal of Vocational Education & Training*, 63(3), 439–449. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13636820.2011.572173>
- International Telecommunication Union (ITU) (2022). *World Telecommunication/ICT Indicators Database*. <https://datahub.itu.int/>
- Kuckartz, U., & McWhertor, A. (2014). *Qualitative text analysis: A guide to methods, practice & using software*. SAGE.
- Lave, J., & Wenger, E. (1991). *Situated learning: Legitimate peripheral participation*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511815355>

Biographical notes

Dr **Léna Krichewsky-Wegener** is a senior TVET researcher and consultant at the Institute for Innovation and Technology (iit) Berlin. Her fields of interest are international cooperation in VET and the international comparative analysis of VET systems.

Lukas Brück has a background in education policies, instructional design and pedagogy. He works as a digital learning consultant in the 'Education Skills and Employment' department at GFA where he develops Digital Learning modules & consults on Digital Learning, digitalisation of education and on digital innovation for GFA projects. Before joining GFA in 2020, Lukas worked for Robert Bosch Foundation and as a short term expert for the Global Partnership for Education.